

Fall 2024

University of Lethbridge: Academic Writing Program

Course: Writing 1000 D
Location: UH D632
Instructor: Frank Onuh
Office: UH A840C
Student Hours: Th 1:30 - 2:30 pm
 or by appointment

Introduction to Academic Writing
Day: Tues 3:00 – 4:15 pm

Phone: (403) 360-1324

The University is located on traditional Blackfoot Confederacy territory. We, as people living and benefiting from Blackfoot Confederacy traditional territory, honour the traditions of people who have cared for this land since time immemorial, as well as all Aboriginal peoples who have helped shape and continue to strengthen our community.

Course Objectives and Learning Outcomes:

Writing 1000 is designed to help students develop the critical thinking, reading, and writing skills that they will use throughout their university careers. Through the study of rhetoric and the analysis of texts, students will develop a greater understanding of and competence in the ways and means of communication. Students will learn strategies for summary, analysis, and persuasion, with particular emphasis placed on writing research papers. In addition, some elements of grammar such as sentence structure will be addressed with a focus on developing a scholarly style. Students should expect content and exercises that reinforce the processes of academic reading, reasoning, and writing. We will also consider the various rhetorical, analytical and citation practices used in academic community.

This semester our writing exercises and discussions will often use technology as a context. As AI increasingly influences various aspects of our lives, it provides a rich source of current, interdisciplinary topics for this course. Through our readings and assignments, we will explore how technology impact is discussed across scholarly disciplines, using these texts as models for effective academic writing and as springboards for developing your own writing skills.

Throughout the course we will address several major questions: how does language work grammatically, stylistically, and socially? How can we use language effectively to communicate (complex) ideas and achieve particular effects for various audiences and situations? How is knowledge constructed and presented in academic contexts? The central focus of the course is on developing strong academic writing skills, but we will use the technology topics to practise these skills to help you become a more critical reader, successful writer, and confident communicator. I also hope that you will gain a stronger understanding of the ways in which technology shapes our lives—our attitudes, values, perceptions and identities—as well as the lives of others around us.

Learning Outcomes:

Upon successful completion of this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the research culture of academia, identify the ways scholarly genres (e.g., articles, critiques, monographs, etc.) reflect and construct that culture, and recognise scholarly texts as conversations that assess existing knowledge and produce new knowledge

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- Demonstrate competence in scholarly citation practices, including integration (applying signal phrases and managing quotations, paraphrases, and summaries) and documentation (referencing sources fully and ethically according to a current scholarly documentation system, such as APA and Chicago)
- Demonstrate competence in scholarly conventions of syntax, grammar, punctuation, diction, and spelling
- Apply a university-level writing process: prewriting, planning, multiple drafting, conferring, integrating research, revising, editing, and proofreading
- Demonstrate information literacy and competence in scholarly research practices, including finding, evaluating, and synthesising primary and secondary source material
- Analyse texts and evaluate controlling ideas, supporting ideas, dominant rhetorical patterns, tone, context, and features of style
- Participate in scholarly conversation as novices by designing and producing a research paper that develops a topic into a thesis, provides suitable authority and context, and presents logically argued, evidence-based, and persuasively organised paragraphs, following academic conventions

Required Texts:

- Stumm, *Joining the Dialogue: Practices for Ethical Research Writing*. (978-1554813957)
- Selected readings (on Moodle)

Grading Scheme:

Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Poor	Minimal Pass	Fail
A+ 90-100	B+ 77-79	C+ 67-69	D+ 55-59	D 50-54	F 49 or less
A 85-89	B 73-76	C 63-66			
A- 80-84	B- 70-72	C- 60-62			

Evaluation:

- In-Class Summary 10
- Critical Summary 15
- In-Class Rhetorical Analysis 10
- Annotated Bibliography 15
- Research Paper and Portfolio 30
- Classroom Engagement 20

Assignment Overview:

- **In-Class Summary (10%):** Students will summarise a scholarly article in approximately 250 words, adhering to APA style guidelines for formatting and documentation. The summary is to be completed in class (or in the Moodle Testing Centre).

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- **Critical Summary (15%):** Students will revise and expand their in-class summary and add a brief evaluation of the assigned scholarly article in 500 – 600 words, adhering to APA style guidelines for formatting and documentation. The assignment helps students to improve professional citation (including expert referencing) and to develop revision skills, including responding to instructor feedback.
- **In-Class Rhetorical Analysis (10%):** Students will write a brief rhetorical analysis (app. 350–500 words) in which they analyse an assigned text’s dominant rhetorical patterns, tone, context, and features of style in response to an assigned prompt. The analysis will be completed in the Moodle Testing Centre.
- **Annotated Bibliography (15%):** Students will write a brief overview (350 – 500 words) outlining their intentions for the research paper. The overview should clearly outline details like topic, purpose/underlining research questions, materials, tentative claims/hypotheses, and the relevance or application of the research in relation to knowledge production and/or problem solving. Along with the overview, students will write an annotated bibliography that summarizes and evaluates 3 scholarly sources they plan to use in their research papers. Each annotation will be approximately 150 – 250 words.
- **Research Paper and Portfolio (30%):** Students will develop a 1500 – 1750-word essay (approximately 5 – 6 pages) in response to a selected topic (as outlined in the Research Paper Assignment Description) in which they will analyse, critique, and synthesize several sources (especially scholarly texts) while developing an original argument related to course themes and objectives. Along with their completed essay, students must submit a portfolio containing outlines, notes, drafts, and a brief reflection on their writing process. The portfolio is meant to showcase the development of your research paper from initial plans to final draft as well as your development as a writer. The expectation is that students demonstrate their planning, drafting, and revising process with the materials they include. The portfolio will be worth 5%, and the final draft of the research paper will be worth 25%. Students who fail to submit a portfolio along with their research paper will not have their final paper assessed.
- **Class Engagement (20%):** This grade is comprised of brief drafting, writing, and/or grammar (15%), participation (3%), and completion of the Library Modules [on Moodle] (2%). Participation will be determined by preparation, attentiveness, attendance, engagement in discussion, and completion of online lessons. **Students who fail to complete online lessons, and/or are habitually late or absent, disruptive, unprepared, or disrespectful of the values and practices of scholarly culture in the university classroom will forfeit a portion or all their participation mark.**

Detailed descriptions of assignments will be provided on Moodle in due time.

Course Schedule:

The course schedule lists the major topics, readings, and assignment due dates. It is designed to facilitate students’ progress, but due to variations in class pace and discussion, **I reserve the right to shift dates if necessary.**

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Writing 1000 D is designed to be a blended synchronous and asynchronous course. The dates listed below are for our scheduled in-person meetings. **Students should complete all assigned readings and video lessons listed for the week before our scheduled meetings** so that they can come prepared for in-person discussion, review, and writing activities. Asynchronous content can be found on Moodle, listed by week.

Weeks	Topics and Assignment Due Dates	Readings and Videos
Week 1 Sept. 10	Introductions	Course overview, expectations, objectives Readings: Stumm “Preface” pp. 7-13 Definition, purpose, types and characteristics of academic writing
Week 2 Sept. 17	Sentence Basics and Punctuations	Readings: Kolln and Gray “Coordination and Subordination” (Chap. 4) (Moodle) Video Lessons: Grammar, phrases, clauses, sentence patterns
Week 3 Sept. 24	Foundations of Academic Discourse	Academic genres and research culture and entering scholarly debates Readings: Stumm Chapter 9; Graff et al. “They Say/I Say” Ch. 1-2 (Moodle)
Week 4 Oct. 1	Reading Scholarship and Writing Summaries <i>In-Class Summary at Testing Center</i>	Readings: Graff et al. “The art of summarizing” pp. 32-44 (Moodle) Article for Summary: Graff et al. “How smartphones Hijack our minds” (Moodle) Video Lessons: Active Reading and Annotation; Writing an Academic Summary
Week 5 Oct. 8	Topic Development and Research Foundations <i>Critical Summary – Submit via Moodle</i>	Topic development Readings: Booth et al. “The Craft of Research” pp. 33-47 (Moodle)
Week 6 Oct. 15	Rhetorical Analysis <i>Rhetorical Analysis at Testing Center</i>	Readings: Foss “Rhetorical Criticism” (Moodle) Article for analysis: Graff et al. “Social Media: The screen, the brain and human nature” pp. 607-612 (Moodle)

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		Video lessons: Introduction to rhetoric, identifying strategies and rhetorical criticism
Week 7 Oct. 22	Finding and Working with Sources; APA Style	Readings: Stumm Ch. 6; “Ethical citation: acknowledging others in a conversation”; Booth et al. “Incorporating sources” pp. 200-2011 (Moodle) For APA information, see OWL Purdue
Week 8 Oct. 29	Planning Research Papers <i>Annotated Biography due: Submit online via Moodle</i>	Stumm Ch. 5; Guptill “Constructing the Thesis and Argument” (Moodle); Lamott “Shitty First Drafts” (Moodle) Video Lessons: Proposal Writing; Synthesizing Sources; Planning and Drafting Research Papers
Week 9 Nov. 5	Drafting: Intros & Cores	Stumm Ch.11 & 12; Booth et al. pp.232-245 See OWL Purdue Developing Strong Thesis Statement
Week 10 Nov. 11-15	Reading Week: No Classes	
Week 11 Nov. 19	Academic Critique and Argumentation	Readings: Stumm “Claims, Reasons and Reasonings” (Ch. 7); Booth et al. “Making Claims” (pp.122-131) (Moodle)
Week 12 Nov. 26	Drafting: Cores & Conclusions; Scholarly Style <i>Research Paper and Portfolio due: Submit online via Moodle</i>	Readings: Stumm Ch. 13; Graff et al. “The Art of Metacommentary” (Moodle) Video lessons: Using metacommentary to strengthen academic arguments and transitioning between ideas in academic writing
Week 13 Dec. 3	Review and Revision	Graff et al. “Revising Substantially” pp. 149-171 (Moodle); Stumm Ch. 14 (Pp. 315-337)
Dec. 7th: Final Research Paper Due		

Assignments:

Assignments are due on the date specified on the schedule above or Moodle. Major assignments must be typed in 12-point font (Times New Roman is standard), double-spaced with 1-inch margins, and otherwise formatted according to APA conventions.

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Unless otherwise stated, students will submit assignments as PDF documents to Moodle. Other file formats will not be accepted. **Please do not email your assignments without prior discussion** (it is very easy for emailed assignments to get overlooked as I get many emails).

Submissions that do not agree with the standards above may be returned for revision and thus risk incurring a late penalty.

You will be given adequate notice of all due dates and topics for assignments. Time constraints do not permit extensions on assignments in this course unless **arranged with me prior to the deadline**; students seeking extensions may be asked to provide **official documentation** to support their request. **Papers arriving after the due date will not receive rigorous comments or corrections**, and late assignments will not be accepted without a **5-mark per day penalty** (including weekends) unless you make prior arrangements for a serious reason, or you have a valid medical certificate.

Grading Policy:

The grades each student earns in this course are determined by the quality of her/his/their work; read the **evaluative rubric** (end of syllabus) to better understand how written work, especially the research paper, will be evaluated.

Students can normally expect a two-week waiting period before marked work is returned.

Please note that **the course is cumulative**. This means that I will hold the later assignments to a higher standard than the early ones. Thorough comments will be provided on some assignments, and students are expected to implement the suggestions from these comments to the best of their abilities on future work.

Students have the opportunity to earn a 1% bonus on their overall course grade. To qualify for this bonus, please email me a meme related to artificial intelligence by September 25. This is a fun way to explore the impact of AI on society and technology while also practicing professional email communication. Please ensure that your email adheres to the email etiquette outlined in the syllabus. This is also a great opportunity to introduce yourself if you haven't already.

Guidelines and Expectations:

Students should expect lessons, discussion, and exercises that reinforce the processes of academic reading, reasoning, and writing. **Students are expected to have read all the assigned materials before coming to class and to come to class prepared with assigned readings.**

Students are expected to attend class regularly as outlined on the syllabus, to complete assigned video lessons on Moodle, to be punctual for in-person classes, and to actively participate in class discussion and writing exercises. Core information will be given in weekly lessons, and students will not be able to keep up with assignments if they fail to complete these lessons or attend class as assigned. Each student is responsible for all the material covered in videos, readings, activities, and live discussion, as well as any schedule changes announced via Moodle. In the case of serious illness or a major crisis, students should inform me as soon as possible and submit the appropriate documentation. Students are encouraged to contact me as soon as possible with questions or concerns about course material rather than letting problems accumulate.

Students are responsible for following the U of Lethbridge's "Principles of Student Citizenship" (see https://www.uleth.ca/sites/ross/files/imported/policies/student_citizenship.pdf). As you

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respond to other students' contributions in class or on Moodle, you can help to create an atmosphere that encourages positive inquiry and the free exchange of ideas. Please respond thoughtfully and be considerate of the right of others to their own ideas and beliefs.

Students enrolled in this course are subject to and are expected to be familiar with current university policies, including health and safety guidelines and all “Academic Regulations, Policies, and Program Requirements” outlined in the current University of Lethbridge Calendar [<https://www.uleth.ca/ross/academic-calendar>]. This includes matters related to academic regulations, grade appeal policy, student discipline policy for academic and non-academic offences, registration privileges, add/drop and withdrawal deadlines, university property, examination policy and procedures, student computer literacy, as well as appeals related to policy other than grade or student discipline.

Equity Statement:

I am committed to equity, diversity, inclusion, and access for all students in this course, and I have endeavoured to create a safe, inclusive learning environment for us. An inclusive space provides our authentic selves to grow, excel, and prosper. I expect students to contribute to shaping and fostering an optimal teaching/learning environment, and to that end (and in addition to the above), I will not tolerate sexist, homophobic, transphobic, racist, or otherwise bigoted speech in the classroom or in our online learning environment (i.e., Moodle). Please feel free to reach out to me to discuss how I may better support you in your learning or in fostering an equitable, comfortable learning space.

Email Policy:

In general, please check the syllabus, Moodle announcements, or assignment descriptions before emailing me questions about readings, schedule/due dates, or assignments. **If your question can be easily answered by checking these resources, I may not reply to your email.**

Students are expected to correspond with me in a professional manner, including following email conventions (**subject line, greeting, text, and closing**). Please limit your emails to serious matters relevant to the course. Please note that I will not review drafts of written work via email; students are encouraged to meet with me during office hours (or by scheduled appointment) to discuss specific components of their writing or writing process (**see Office Hours policy below**). Students can expect a response to emails within 24 to 48 hours during the week (business hours: 9 – 5). *Please note that emails sent after 5 pm Friday are unlikely to receive a reply until the following Monday morning.*

Office Hours:

Students are welcome and encouraged to drop by my office to see me during regular office hours. Otherwise, you are welcome to email me to request an appointment outside of my regular office hours, and I will do my best to accommodate. Please note that I am not always available to meet at times other than those listed on the syllabus.

Meetings will be kept to approximately 20 minutes in length so that I can accommodate all students throughout the term. **Time constraints do not allow for me to review complete drafts of assignments, but I am happy to offer advice on specific components of written work, such as paragraphs or thesis statements, or the writing process more generally.** I am also available to meet with students for an essay post-mortem: that is, a meeting to dissect their recent work and

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discuss how to improve. Please make an appointment with the **Writing Centre** tutor for more extensive one-on-one writing tutoring (link below).

Academic Integrity:

The academic enterprise is founded on **honesty, civility, and integrity**. As members of this enterprise, all students are expected to know, understand, and follow the codes of conduct regarding academic integrity. At the most basic level, this means submitting only original work done by you and acknowledging all sources of information or ideas and attributing them to others as required. This also means you should not cheat, copy, or mislead others about what is your work. Violations of academic integrity (i.e., misconduct) lead to the breakdown of the academic enterprise, and therefore serious consequences arise, and harsh sanctions are imposed.

Artificial Intelligence:

Our primary goal in this course is to enhance your critical thinking, reading, and writing abilities. While generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools (e.g., ChatGPT) can solve a range of written tasks, they limit human participation in the writing process. As Writing 1000 is designed to develop your own critical thinking, reading, and writing skills, if you rely solely on generative AI tools to complete the course assignments, you will miss your learning and minimize your personal intellectual development. However, understanding and using AI ethically in academic contexts is becoming increasingly important. Therefore, while the use of generative AI tools to write assignments is totally prohibited unless explicitly stated otherwise by the instructor, students are encouraged to explore its other ethical uses. For example, it can be used for brainstorming ideas, providing language or grammar support, and offering feedback or revisions on drafts. Engaging with AI in these ways can provide valuable insights and complement your learning experience. It is crucial to maintain academic integrity and ensure that all submitted work reflects your own understanding and skills. **If you are unsure of a particular use case, seek clarifications from your instructor.**

Plagiarism:

Plagiarism is a serious academic offence and **is defined as any representation by a student of the words, ideas, images, or data of another as his/her/their own**. Plagiarism will not be tolerated in this course. Students should note that plagiarism is not limited to copying from printed material; copying from the Internet or from material submitted for another course are also examples of plagiarism.

Students guilty of plagiarism **will receive a grade of “F” for the assignment; they may also receive a grade of “F” in the course**. Other penalties such as academic suspension or expulsion may also apply. Please note that a letter indicating that the student has committed plagiarism on an assignment or has cheated on a quiz will be automatically sent the Dean’s office. A more detailed description of the U of L’s policies and procedures for dealing with academic misconduct may be found in the current Academic Calendar or via the link below (<https://www.ulethbridge.ca/policy/resources/student-discipline-policy-academic-offences-undergraduate-students>).

Please note: As part of our commitment to academic integrity, all written submissions for this course will be checked using an AI writing detection tool to verify the originality of the work. It

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is essential that all assignments reflect your own understanding and voice. Plagiarism or submission of work that is not your own will not be tolerated and may result in disciplinary action.

Electronic Resources:

Writing and Citing Guides: <http://libguides.uleth.ca/cite>

Oxford English Dictionary Online: At <http://www.uleth.ca/lib/>, enter “OED” under “Search” (use the recommended database: Oxford English Dictionary listed at the top of the results) Ulrich’s Periodicals Directory: At <http://www.uleth.ca/lib/>, enter “Ulrich’s” under “Search”

OWL Purdue: For excellent general writing tips, see the Online Writing Lab (OWL), Purdue University: <http://owl.english.purdue.edu/>

Useful University of Lethbridge Services:

Students with a disability or health consideration are encouraged to contact the Accommodated Learning Centre for support: <http://www.uleth.ca/ross/accommodated-learning-centre/>

The U of Lethbridge Academic Writing Centre offers free services for student writers, including help with assignments. This semester, tutoring services are available in person. You are strongly encouraged to take advantage of this resource. To book an appointment, go to the website: <http://www.uleth.ca/artsci/academic-writing/writing-centre>

The intensity of university studies can take a psychological toll. The university’s Counselling services are ready and available to address any mental health concerns. You can make an appointment here: <http://www.uleth.ca/counselling/content/booking-appointment>. If you are unsure about that option but are concerned that your mental health is a barrier to your studies, please contact me personally.

Rubric for Assessment of Written Work**Excellent (A Range)**

An excellent paper shows an exceptional ability to communicate clearly and effectively to a specific audience. This paper fully answers the question posed in the assignment and follows the guidelines given for that assignment, including formatting and referencing requirements; when applicable, it develops and advances an intelligent and “original” thesis/position; when applicable, it demonstrates solid, thorough, and comprehensive research. There is a smooth integration of sources (using summary, paraphrase, and quotation); the paper demonstrates a controlled movement through the levels of high-level ideas and supportive, specific details; it effectively defines key terms/abstractions and explains reasoning. The paper is clearly and logically organised: i.e., its paragraphs are unified and coherent, and transitions between paragraphs are smooth and effective. The sentences are clear, concise, easy to follow, and varied in structure to compel interest; it uses an extensive and sophisticated vocabulary; the language of this paper is clear and precise; there are next to no sentence-level, documentation, or format errors. This paper demonstrates a sophisticated and sustained understanding of and engagement with scholarly style and scholarly knowledge-making practices.

Good (B Range)

A good paper shows a strong ability to communicate clearly and effectively to a specific audience. This paper adequately answers the question posed in the assignment and follows the guidelines given for that assignment, including formatting and referencing requirements; when applicable, it

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advances a reasonable thesis/position; it incorporates source evidence but does not critically evaluate it as effectively as it might. Source material is not always smoothly integrated, and the argument might seem tenuous or discontinuous at times; this paper maintains a reasonable balance of high-level ideas and supportive specific details; it defines key terms/abstractions. Paragraphs are reasonably unified and organised in a coherent order; transitions between paragraphs are acceptable; most of the sentences are clear, concise, and generally easy to follow; some sentences show variety to create interest; this is a solid effort (above average work) with only occasional sentence level, spelling, documentation or formatting errors and minor lapses in argumentation or analysis; its vocabulary is varied but occasionally imprecise or vague. This paper demonstrates a serious (if at times inconsistent) engagement with scholarly style and tries to engage with scholarly knowledge-making practices.

Adequate (C Range)

An adequate paper shows a reasonable ability to communicate adequately to a specific audience although there may be some weaknesses in adaptation. This paper partially or indirectly answers the question posed in the assignment and satisfactorily follows the guidelines given for that particular assignment, including formatting and referencing requirements, but there are some minor imperfections. Its topic is not narrowed effectively, the topic is off-focus for the assignment, and its thesis/position (when applicable) is unclearly stated or only partially developed; it cites the minimum number of sources as evidence, but that evidence might seem pasted into the body or argument of the paper and not critically incorporated and evaluated; there is little (or rudimentary and repetitive) integration of sources; this paper moves awkwardly and unclearly between its high-level ideas and specific details. It lacks effective and scholarly definitions of key abstractions; often it is predominantly descriptive or expository (a list of specific details with no clear high-level ideas to organise them), or it is flawed due to having too many high-level ideas or generalisations with little or no specific detail to support them. This paper is flawed by sentence-level errors, spelling errors, and formatting errors, which suggest it was not carefully proofread. It tends to generalise (about “life,” “society,” etc.) instead of analysing/persuading. Its paragraphs are not strongly unified; there is some organisational breakdown between paragraphs, hence the paper lacks coherence (i.e., the paper needs stronger transitions between sentences and paragraphs); the sentences may vary in quality, with some being clear, but others being wordy or hard to follow; vocabulary is uneven (incorrect use of words, obvious and ineffective reliance upon an electronic thesaurus, etc.) or repetitive; this paper engages the language of scholarly style intermittently and inconsistently. Though the adequate paper may exhibit one or more of these weaknesses, the intended audience, with some effort, is still able to understand the intent of the paper.

Poor (D Range)

A poor paper communicates marginally successfully to a specific audience, with several weaknesses in adaptation. Though the weaknesses are significant, the paper demonstrates enough strength overall to receive a passing grade. This paper does not clearly answer the question posed in the assignment and/or may not follow the assignment guidelines, including formatting and referencing requirements; if applicable, it lacks a narrowed topic and clearly stated thesis/position; this paper is often predominantly descriptive with little or no analysis, evaluation, or persuasion; it does not cite adequate source evidence, and relies heavily on uncritical “cutting and pasting” from non-scholarly sources; it tends to use few, if any, scholarly secondary sources. There is no clear sense of organisation or relation between high-level ideas and specific details; this paper commits serious sentence-level errors (coordinating, subordinating, punctuation, etc.); it poses

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numerous spelling and word-choice errors; it relies heavily on generalisations and the rhetoric of self-expression/personal opinion; its paragraphs lack unity, and there is no clear order or smooth transition between them (hence the paper lacks coherence); its vocabulary is limited as is its sentence structure (i.e., an overuse of simple sentences); there are numerous careless errors in the documentation and formatting of the paper, etc.; there is no evidence of editing/revision. This paper seems to be written in a hurry with little research or editorial revision, and it does not engage the language and practices of scholarly style effectively.

Failure (F)

This paper does not answer the question posed in the assignment, nor does it meet the minimum requirements stated in the assignment description. A failing paper exhibits one or more the following characteristics to the extent that it would be unacceptable to the audience for whom it is intended: it does not develop a narrow topic nor clearly state a thesis (when applicable); the reasoning in this paper is difficult—or impossible—to follow; it does not provide adequate research in the form of source evidence, nor does it integrate evidence; usually, little or no scholarly research has been done to support the thesis; there is no organised movement and logical connection between its high-level ideas and specific details; this paper could be plagiarised work; paragraphs lack unity (they are not about “one thing”) and are poorly organised and incoherent—i.e., they jump around and lack a clear, logical order. There are consistent sentence-level errors; predominant generalisations about the topic abound; there is no evidence of in-depth analysis, editing/revision, or scholarly engagement/research. This paper is compromised by copious and careless spelling and word choice errors, formatting errors, etc., and it does not engage the practice and style of scholarly thinking and writing in a serious way. A failing paper may demonstrate a significant lack of understanding of the assignment or the writing process and/or a failure to implement appropriate communication skills. Sources may be used incorrectly and there may be egregious citation errors. Instances of plagiarism will be treated as Academic Misconduct and dealt with accordingly. **Any paper that does not meet the basic requirements of university writing cannot receive a passing grade.**

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